

Event metadata

Event title	The Technician Commitment: Championing technical skills, roles and careers
Event type	Webinar
Date of event	12/02/2026
Time of event	10am AEDT
Topic description	<p>The Technician Commitment is an internationally recognised higher education and research sector initiative that is driving culture change for the technical community. Multiple Australian organisations are signatories demonstrating their commitment to ensuring visibility, recognition, career development and sustainability for technicians working in higher education and research, across all disciplines.</p> <p>Associate Lead, Dr Simon Breeden joins us to discuss the background, development and impact of the Commitment across 4 key areas – Visibility, Recognition, Career Development, and Sustainability.</p>
Format description	Webinar presentation followed by a brief question and answer session
Identifier(s)/URL	https://www.biocommons.org.au/events/technician-commitment-2026
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Keywords	<p>Research Infrastructure Skilled Workforce Career Development Higher Education</p>
Contact	training@biocommons.org.au
Audience	This webinar is for everyone and is especially relevant to technical professionals, managers and leaders in

	higher education, research or research infrastructure across all sectors.
Prerequisites	None
Technical requirements	None
Learning outcomes	By the end of this webinar you should have a greater understanding of the Technician Commitment and how it is driving culture change in the UK, Australia and internationally to promote visibility, recognition and sustainability of technical roles and the impact it has had in higher education and research
Speakers	Dr Simon Breeden, Associate Lead, Technician Commitment
Training materials	<p>Materials shared in this Zenodo record:</p> <p>SWB Bio Commons - Australia (11-02-26) (PDF): Slides presented during the webinar.</p> <p>Technician Commitment Webinar Q&A (PDF): Answers to questions submitted during the webinar that Dr Simon Breeden has provided written responses to.</p> <p>Materials shared elsewhere:</p> <p>A recording of this webinar is available on the Australian BioCommons YouTube channel: https://youtu.be/LCmlH88JwC8</p>
Related material	None